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Terms, definitions and abbreviated terms

List of project participants

Participant organisation name	Country
Polytechnic Institute of Setúbal (IPS)	PT
St. Pölten University of Applied Sciences (STPUAS)	AT
Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences (MATE)	HU
Politehnica University of Timisoara (UPT)	RO
University Colleges Leuven Limburg (UCLL)	BE
Vidzeme University of Applied Sciences (ViA)	LV

Abbreviated terms

CA – Consortium Agreement

DoA – Description of Action

DMP – Data Management Plan

E³UDRES² – Engaged European Entrepreneurial University as Driver for European Smart and Sustainable Regions

EB – Executive Board

GA – Grant Agreement

GnA – General Assembly

HR – Human Resources

HRS4R – Human Resources Strategy for Research

KoM – Kick-off Meeting

OA – Open Access

OE – Open Education

OI – Open Innovation

OS – Open Science

PC – Project Coordinator

PM – Person-Month

RI – Research Infrastructures

RP – Reporting Period

SWOT – Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats

WP – Work Package

Executive Summary

E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators is a project where the main goal is to increase the research capacity of the institutions that form the European University alliance E³UDRES². This increase in capacity is based on the Engaged and Entrepreneurial European University as Driver for European Smart and Sustainable Regions and aims to co-create a specific joint research strategy for the alliance. The E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project intends to develop in a sustainable way, a strong interconnection between education, research, innovation, and entrepreneurship. E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators address the region's needs.

This Quality assurance and risk management plan will guide the project's implementation, regarding the effective achievement of its objectives with a minimum of required quality. It is intended that all the activities, tasks, deliverables, and goals can follow what is described in this initial planning and that all partners can guarantee its implementation according to the time schedule, the defined budget and the quality standards required for such a project, and at the same time reducing the risk and enhancing the objectives in the most efficient way. To ensure proper implementation of the plan, the specificities of each Work Package (WP) were considered when defining its procedures.

Considering that risks may appear at any time during the development of the project, due to internal or external threats, a protocol was defined that allows identifying these risks as well as evaluating, monitoring and controlling them.

This document is based on ISO 9001:2008 Quality Management Systems Requirements and is the result of activities developed in Task 1.3.

1 Introduction

1.1 Relation of the quality manual with other documents of the project

The Quality assurance and risk management plan defines all the processes involved in the project, assuring that identifies:

- The required process to the efficiency of the project;
- The systematization of the project objectives;
- Deliverables arising from the work packages;
- Specific needs of the project implementation, such as management structure, management procedures, risk management.

To accomplish this level of definition and task specification, the Quality assurance and risk management plan will consider the Grant Agreement (GA), the Consortium Agreement (CA), the project itself and attachments.

1.2 Document structure

The document consists of the following sections and annexes:

1. **Introduction:** explanation of the purpose and structure of the Monitoring and Evaluation Plan.
2. **Project Overview:** identification of the participating organizations in the project, its objectives, implementation mode and main results.
3. **Monitoring and Evaluation System:** description of the monitoring and evaluation system structure and responsibilities; the improvement cycle to be followed during the project; the processes map and the way they're implemented and monitored (processes management).
4. **Documented Information:** presentation of the project's documents identification, elaboration, approval, dissemination and revision.
5. **Implementation Risks and Mitigation Actions:** presentation of the main project's risks that have been identified and the respective measures to be implemented to avoid or to minimize its impact.

1.3 Document revision

The monitoring of all E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators activities will be based on this Quality assurance and risk management plan provided in the 6th month of the project – and will be periodically systematized in semiannual reports (presented during the project's assembly meetings). All monitoring and evaluation activities will be coordinated by the Polytechnic Institute of Setúbal (IPS) and will count with the contribution of all the participating organizations (one element per partner). The Quality assurance and risk management plan will be reviewed annually or more often, whenever necessary.

Note: As it is important to have a Quality assurance and risk management plan from the beginning of the project to guide the project work team, the IPS will present a draft version of the plan at the kick-off meeting (KoM), which will serve to guide the development of the project work, until the final version is produced (month 6) and at the same time it will serve as a work base to produce the final version, with the contribution of all partners.

2 Project overview

2.1 Participating organizations

List of project participants

Participant organization name	Acronym	Country
Polytechnic Institute of Setúbal	IPS	Portugal
St. Pölten University of Applied Sciences	STPUAS	Austria
Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences	MATE	Hungary
Politehnica University of Timisoara	UPT	Romania
University Colleges Leuven Limburg	UCLL	Belgium
Vidzeme University of Applied Sciences	ViA	Latvia

2.2 Objectives

In line with its vision, mission, core values, culture, and principles the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project aims to co-create a more specific joint research and innovation strategy and a common agenda to accelerate the transformation into a European multi-institutional Research and Innovation Hub for Smart and Sustainable Regions. E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators includes, interacts, and collaborates with a diverse variety of smart and ambitious people, academic institutions, regional authorities, companies, European R&I networks and regional innovation ecosystems. E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators is committed to scientific excellence and research integrity within its cross-disciplinary and cross-sectoral key R&I networks and promotes (future) R&I competences, skills, resources, methods, training, services and management for collaborative research and open innovation for smart and sustainable regions.

The project will work on the following **transformation modules**:

- Co-creation of a Common Research and Innovation Strategy (WP2)
- Sharing Research Infrastructures (WP3)
- Embracing Open Science and Open Education (WP4)
- Creating proximity and engaging citizens and society (WP5)
- Strengthening R&I human resources and ecosystems (WP6)

Working along parallel but converging lines over these transformation modules, we expect to jointly achieve the following **objectives**:

- **Objective 1:** Co-create a common strategy and agenda that unlocks our potential for excellence in Research and Innovation, to accelerate the transformation into a multi-institutional European Research and Innovation Centre for Smart and Sustainable Regions;
- **Objective 2:** Develop best practices and a strategy for pooling research infrastructures (RI), expertise, data and resources and for collaborating with/getting access to other strategic research infrastructures;
- **Objective 3:** Develop structured support programmes aimed at empowering our scientific communities to fully embrace Open Science, Open Innovation, Open Education, Engaged Science and Engaged Education;
- **Objective 4:** Work to achieve a level playing field in terms of institutional strategies and policies for Human Resources for Research, from which we will be able to address bigger challenges, such as brain mobility, new career assessments and joint recruitment strategies;
- **Objective 5:** Develop a structured and integrated framework to seamlessly link all our R&I ecosystems and the E³UDRES² alliance's knowledge triangle of education, research and innovation;
- **Objective 6:** Along our pathway to build a common R&I agenda, be connected and dialogue with peer Alliances and HEIs, HEI associations and advocacy groups, and policy-makers with a view to contribute with evidence based results to the co-creation of future EEA/ERA work programmes and to inform better policies.

2.3 Implementation

The project will be developed for three years and divided in six Work Packages:

Figure 1 – PERT Chart

Table 1 – Work Packages

Work package number	Work package title	Lead participant number	Lead participant short name	Person-months	Start month	End month
1	Project management and dissemination	1	IPS	39	1	36
2	Research and innovation strategy	2	STPUAS	39	1	36
3	Sharing research infrastructures	3	MATE	39	1	36
4	Embracing open science, open innovation and open education	4	UPT	39	2	36
5	Creating proximity and engaging citizens and society	5	UCLL	39	7	36
6	Human resources and R&I ecosystems	6	ViA	39	7	36
Total person-months				234		

The expected outcomes are as follows:

- 1) The development of **joint strategies** for E³UDRES² R&I dimension, associated to the following **transformation modules**:
 - o R&I networks, groups, research lines and activities – **WP2**
 - o Sharing and gaining access to (external) research infrastructures (including e-infrastructures) – **WP3**

- o Open science, open education and open innovation – **WP4**
 - o Engaging citizens and society – **WP5**
 - o Human resources for research and R&I ecosystems – **WP6**
- 2) The development of **joint implementation plans** for each transformation module;
- 3) **Run some pilots:** training and engagement actions/programmes.

3 Monitoring and evaluation system

3.1 Structure and responsibilities

For the operationalization of the **Monitoring and Evaluation System**, the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project defined a structure that intends to be permanently adapted to the needs of management, monitoring and evaluation of the processes, assuring an effective and integrated action of its elements. The system is a responsibility of the Project Coordinator (PC), who articulates semiannually¹ the data collection with all partners (one designated element per partner). The process is described in P5. *Measurement, Evaluation and Improvement*. The Quality assurance and risk management plan – framing document of the monitoring and evaluation system – is, thus, provided (and reviewed) by the project's coordination team, in articulation with all project's partners, to guarantee its permanent update to the implementation of the project, according with the specificities of the different WPs.

3.2 Improvement cycle

To achieve a greater efficiency and continuous improvement of its performance, E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project's implementation follows the PDCA improvement cycle:

- **Plan:** actions' planning is based on project's documentation, and it is described in the Monitoring and Evaluation Plan.
- **Do:** actions' implementation follows the project's documentation and the processes' timetables and procedures (Process Overview/Monitoring and Evaluation Plan).
- **Check:** project's periodic monitoring and evaluation is based on the analysis of indicators and the level of implementation of actions (considering the feedback of project's partners and/or external evaluators and/or European Commission, when applicable).
- **Act:** the improvement actions are defined by the Project Coordinator (with partners collaboration) and implemented as planned, according to the situation.

3.3 Processes map

According to a process approach, E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators integrates 5 interrelated processes, to ensure the effectiveness of project' implementation and organization:

- P1. Management and Coordination
- P2. Financial Management

¹ In some situations, there may be an intermediate monitoring.

- P3. Implementation
- P4. Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
- P5. Measurement, Evaluation and Improvement

Figure 2 – Processes map

To assure a more effective control and a more effective monitoring some processes include subprocesses.

Table 2 – Processes map

Processes	Subprocesses
P1. Management and Coordination	SP1.1 – Coordination activities SP1.2 – Project reporting
P2. Financial Management	NA
P3. Implementation	SP3.1 – R&I networks, groups, research lines and activities SP3.2 – Sharing and gaining access to (external) research infrastructures (including e-infrastructures) SP3.3 – Open science, open education, and open innovation SP3.4 – Engaging citizens and society SP3.5 – Human resources for research and R&I ecosystems
P4. Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation	NA
P5. Measurement, Evaluation and Improvement	NA

3.4 Processes management

P1. Management and Coordination

Figure 3 – P1. Management and coordination

E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project implements management and coordination activities in an integrated way. With a three-year duration, the project includes a Management and Coordination process that involves two interrelated subprocesses to ensure that the results are achieved. Within this Process, the Project Coordinator is responsible for all communication and overall management of the project activities carried out by partners, and for the contact with the European Commission.

Table 3 – SP1.1 – Coordination activities

SP1.1 | Coordination activities
Leader Partner: **IPS**

Subprocess overview	A1.1 Assure the supervision and coordination of project's activities	IPS
	A1.2 Assure the project's meetings management	

Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Description of Action (projects formal documentation) 			Start: 01/10/2022 End: 30/09/2025 Partner: IPS
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Efficient organization of the project Meeting Plan 			
Activity	Partner	Activity Indicators	Global Indicators	Associated Documents
A1.1 Assure the supervision and coordination of project's activities	IPS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ≥ 80% of the activities implemented on schedule by the lead partner(s) 90% of the milestones achieved on schedule 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ≥ 80% of the process's activities done as planned 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monitoring & Evaluation Plan M&E Semi-Annual reports
A1.2 Assure the project's meetings management		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ≥ 80% of the scheduled meetings (WP1 and others) ≥ 85% of the scheduled ExB meetings = 100% of the scheduled GnA meetings ≥ 75% of the expected number of participants in the meetings 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Agendas Minutes Attendance lists Certificates

Table 4 – SP1.2 – Project reporting

SP1.2 | Project reporting
Leader Partner: **IPS**

Subprocess overview	A2 Assure the project's periodic reporting (Technical and Financial Reporting)	IPS
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Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Description of Action (projects formal documentation) 			Start: 01/10/2022 End: 30/09/2025 Partner: IPS
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Efficient organization of the project Meeting Plan 			
Activity	Partner	Activity Indicators	Global Indicators	Associated Documents
A2 Assure the project's periodic reporting (Technical and Financial Reporting)	IPS	NA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 100% of the reports approved on schedule by the PC (30 days before the deadline) 100% of the reports submitted on schedule to the EC 100% EC approval of the report first version 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interim Report 60 days after end of 1st reporting period 31/12/2023 - (03/03/2024) Final Report 60 days after project ending 30/09/2025 - (30/11/2025)

P2. Financial Management

Figure 4 – P2. Financial Management

“Financial management” process includes all the activities that ensure the existence and availability of financial resources during project’s implementation. Seeking a systematic financial management and ensuring maximum precision in the management of funds assigned to the project, the process includes two main activities – 1) Pre-financing/Funds distribution; 2) Costs control and Reporting – to ensure that all partners accomplish its implementation according to planned.

Table 5 – P2. Financial Management

P2. Financial Management

Leader Partner: **IPS**

Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Incoming funds ▪ Annex II Grant Agreement 			Start: 01/10/2022 End: 30/09/2025 Partner: IPS
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Funds distributions ▪ Financial project rules met by all partners 			
Activity	Partner	Activity Indicators	Global Indicators	Associated Documents
A1 Pre-financing/ Funds distribution	IPS/All partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ ≥ 80% of the funds distributed by IPS on schedule 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 100% partner's participation ▪ ≥ 80% of the process's activities done as planned 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Transfer confirmation
A2 Costs control and Reporting	IPS/All partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ ≥ 80% of the Confirmation by partners of the time declaration filled every 6 months ▪ ≥ 90% of the partners costs reports delivered to the PC on schedule 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Time declarations ▪ W1 meetings presentations ▪ Form C

P3. Implementation

Figure 5 – P3. Implementation

Process 3 refers to the project’s “Implementation” developed in five main phases, according with the different technical WPs: 1) R&I networks, groups, research lines and activities; 2) Sharing and gaining access to (external) research infrastructures (including e-infrastructures); 3) Open science, open education, and open innovation; 4) Engaging citizens and society; 5) Human resources for research and R&I ecosystems.

Table 6 – SP3.1 – R&I networks, groups, research lines and activities

SP3.1 | R&I networks, groups, research lines and activities

Leader Partner: **STPUAS**

Subprocess overview	A1.1 Understand the current position and Comprehensive SWOT analysis	STPUAS, all participants		
	A1.2 Identify, evaluate and validate strategic options and set objectives and plan implementation			
Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP2 tasks 	Start: 01/10/2022 End: 30/09/2025 Partner: STPUAS		
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP2 deliverables 			
Activity	Partner	Activity Indicators	Global Indicators	Associated Documents
A1.1 Understand the current position and Comprehensive SWOT analysis	STPUAS Supervises, all participants execute	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Report on E³UDRES² alliance R&I landscape finished on schedule 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ≥ 80% of the process's activities done as planned 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Report (09/2023) Compilation document (09/2023) Partners' contributions evidence (09/2023)
A1.2 Identify, evaluate and validate strategic options and set objectives and plan implementation		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1st and 2nd R&I surveys reports finished on schedule ≥ 90% of responses from the representative number of researchers per institution ≥ 80% of responses from the representative number of students and stakeholders per institution Set objectives and plan implementation finished on schedule 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Surveys (06/2023 and 09/2023) Surveys Reports (09/2023 and 03/2024) Compilation document (09/2025) Report (09/2025) Partners' contributions evidence (09/2025)

Table 7 – SP3.2 – Sharing and gaining access to research infrastructures

SP3.2 | Sharing and gaining access to research infrastructures

Leader Partner: **MATE**

Subprocess overview	A2.1 Understand the current position and future situation	MATE, all participants		
	A2.2 Developing a strategy and the implementation plan for a network sharing for efficient, sustainable, and agile implementation			
Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP3 tasks 	Start: 01/10/2022 End: 30/09/2025 Partner: MATE		
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP3 deliverables 			
Activity	Partner	Activity Indicators	Global Indicators	Associated Documents
A2.1 Understand the current position and future situation	MATE Supervises, all participants execute	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Report on the current and future situation ≥ 90% of responses from the representative number of researchers per institution ≥ 80% of relevant internal infrastructures analysed ≥ 70% of indirect infrastructures analysed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ≥ 80% of the process's activities done as planned 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Report, internal infrastructures (09/2023) Report, external infrastructures (03/2024) Compilation document (03/2024) Partners' contributions evidence (03/2024)
A2.2 Developing a strategy and the implementation plan for a network sharing for efficient, sustainable, and agile implementation		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strategy & implementation plan for efficient, sustainable, and agile RD&I sharing network finished on schedule 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Compilation document (09/2025) Report (09/2025) Partners' contributions evidence (09/2025) 	

Table 8 – SP3.3 – Open science, open education, and open innovation

SP3.3 | Open science, open education, and open innovation

Leader Partner: **UPT**

Subprocess overview	A3.1 Understand the current position and comprehensive SWOT analysis	UPT, all participants
	A3.2 Identify, evaluate and validate strategic options and set objectives and plan implementation	
	A3.3 Pilot activities	

Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP4 tasks 			Start: 01/10/2022 End: 30/09/2025 Partner: UPT
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP4 deliverables 			
Activity	Partner	Activity Indicators	Global Indicators	Associated Documents
A3.1 Understand the current position and comprehensive SWOT analysis	UPT Supervises, all participants execute	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Report on current position of E³UDRES² alliance finished on schedule Proposal for joint training curricula for providing OS/OI/OE skills and competences finished on schedule Surveys and interview reports finished on schedule ≥ 90% of responses from the representative number of researchers per institution ≥ 75% of responses from the representative number of students per institution 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ≥ 80% of the process's activities done as planned 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Surveys (01/2023) Surveys Report (05/2023) Report on joint training curricula (09/2023) Report on current situation (05/2023) Compilation document (09/2023) Partners' contributions evidence (09/2023)
A3.2 Identify, evaluate and validate strategic options and set objectives and plan implementation		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Set objectives and plan implementation finished on schedule 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Compilation document (03/2025) Report (03/2025) Partners' contributions evidence (03/2023)

(Continuation)

Inputs		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP4 tasks 			Start: 01/10/2022 End: 30/09/2025 Partner: UPT
Outputs		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP4 deliverables 			
Activity	Partner	Activity Indicators	Global Indicators	Associated Documents	
A3.3 Pilot activities	UPT Supervises, all participants execute	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ≥ 95% of the training activities planned, carried out and on schedule ≥ 90% attendance according to the number expected in the UPT Open Science workshops ≥ 80% attendance according to the number expected in the open Science webinars for all audiences ≥ 80% attendance according to the number expected in the summer school 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ≥ 80% of the process's activities done as planned 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Report on OS/OI/OE pilot training activities (09/2025) Partners' contributions evidence (09/2025) 	

Table 9 – SP3.4 – Engaging citizens and society

SP3.4 | Engaging citizens and society

Leader Partner: **UCLL**

Subprocess overview	A4.1 Collect and co-create engagement models	UCLL, all participants		
	A4.2 Inspire citizens into engagement			
Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP5 tasks 	Start: 01/05/2023 End: 30/09/2025 Partner: UCLL		
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP5 deliverables 			
Activity	Partner	Activity Indicators	Global Indicators	Associated Documents
A4.1 Collect and co-create engagement models	UCLL Supervises, all participants execute	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reports on engagement models finished on schedule 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ≥ 80% of the process's activities done as planned 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Models of engagement guide report (09/2023) Report on maturity model (11/2023) Compilation document (11/2023) Partners' contributions evidence (11/2023)
A4.2 Inspire citizens into engagement		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ≥ 95% of workshops planned, carried out and on schedule Map of 'engagement angels', finished on schedule ≥ 90% of ambassadors identified according to the number planned I-Living Lab (I-LL), carried out on schedule ≥ 85% attendance according to the expected number, in the I-Living Lab (I-LL) 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Report on Inspiration guide (06/2024) Report on Map of 'engagement angels', (06/2024) Report on I-Living Lab (I-LL) (09/2025) Compilation document (09/2025) Partners' contributions evidence (09/2025)

Table 10 – SP3.5 – Engaging citizens and society

SP3.5 | Human resources for research and R&I ecosystems

Leader Partner: **ViA**

Subprocess overview	A4.1 Understand the current position and Comprehensive SWOT analysis	ViA, all participants		
	A4.2 Identify, evaluate, and validate strategic options and set objectives and plan implementation			
Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP6 tasks 	Start: 01/05/2023 End: 30/09/2025 Partner: ViA		
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP6 deliverables 			
Activity	Partner	Activity Indicators	Global Indicators	Associated Documents
A5.1 Understand the current position and comprehensive SWOT analysis	ViA Supervises, all participants execute	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Status report on E³UDRES² partners' human resources for research finished on schedule Status report on E³UDRES² R&I ecosystems finished on schedule ≥ 90% of responses from the representative number of our R&I staff per institution ≥ 80% of responses from the representative number of to stakeholders per institution 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ≥ 80% of the process's activities done as planned 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Surveys (06/2023) Reports (12/2023 and 05/2024) Compilation document (05/2024) Partners' contributions evidence (05/2025)
A5.2 Identify, evaluate, and validate strategic options and Set objectives and plan implementation		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strategy and plan implementation finished on schedule 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reports (05/2025 and 09/2025) Compilation document (09/2025) Partners' contributions evidence (09/2025)

P4. Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation

Figure 6 – P4. Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation

The Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Process, mainly based on the project’s outputs. The process also includes the global monitoring of the communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities.

Table 11 – P4. Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation

P4. Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation

Leader Partner: **IPS**

Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Description of Action (projects formal documentation) 			Start: 01/10/2022
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan Data Management Plan 			End: 30/09/2025 Partner: IPS
Activity	Partner	Activity Indicators	Global Indicators	Associated Documents
A1 Promote an effective communication between partners	IPS Supervises, all participants execute	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Internal communication platform, EMDESK, 100% operational to be used by all partners until month 3 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ≥ 80% of the process's activities done as planned 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EMDESK platform (12/2022)
A2 Promote an effective communication, dissemination, and exploitation considering the external target audiences		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan and its revisions finished on schedule Data Management Plan finished, and its update finished on schedule ≥ 75% of the communication activities implemented as planned ≥ 75% of the dissemination and exploitation activities implemented as planned 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reports/Plans Project website (03/2023) Publications, Social media, Brochures, News letters, and factsheets, Press releases, Open events (09/2025) Surveys, Trainings/Workshops, project website and repositories, Open reports, deliverables and publications, Conferences and meetings (09/2025)
A3 Organization of a science-policy conference		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conference carried out on schedule ≥ 75% attendance according to the expected number 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Report on E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators science-policy conference (03/2025)

The monitoring of communication, dissemination and exploitation activities will be carried out by IPS, within the scope of the *Project Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan*. Thus, the monitoring made under the *Monitoring and Evaluation Plan* (all processes) will only provide a biannual (and aggregated) monitoring of the planned/implemented activities.

P5. Measurement, Evaluation and Improvement

Figure 7 – P5. Measurement, Evaluation and Improvement

Measurement, Evaluation and Improvement process refers to the periodic collection and analysis of the processes' data, and the definition and application of improvement measures to enhance project's implementation and results (if necessary). As mentioned in 3.1 (*Structure and Responsibilities*), the indicators monitoring occurs every 6 months (by the coordination team with the collaboration of one element per partner), in order to gather the data needed to the monitoring and evaluation analysis.

Table 12 – Indicators monitoring schedule

Project implementation Period	Monitoring and Evaluation Date
M01 – M06	M06 – March 2022
M07 – M12	M12 – October 2023
M13 – M18	M18 – March 2024
M19 – M24	M24 – September 2024
M25 – M30	M30 – March 2025
M31 – M36	M36 – September 2025

Table 13 – P5. Measurement, Evaluation and Improvement

P5. Measurement, Evaluation and Improvement

Leader Partner: **IPS**

Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assessment of E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators implementation (indicators' monitoring) 			Start: M1 End: M36 Partner: IPS
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improvement of E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators implementation (measures implementation) 			
Activity	Partner	Activity Indicators	Global Indicators	Associated Documents
A1 Measure and evaluate	IPS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Indicators' results monitoring and analysis on schedule Improvement actions defined on schedule 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Comprehensive analysis of the indicators 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monitoring sheets Occurrence registrations
A2 Improve		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 80% of the improvement actions implemented on schedule 90% of the complaints assessed/given feedback in 20 days 		

Complaint Management

If there are any complaint, either from the partners or from another interested party involved in the project's execution, it must be registered by the person who receives it in the Occurrence Registration. An analysis of the cause of the complaint must be done with the claimant. After analyzing the cause of the complaint, all information should be sent to the project coordinator, who analyzes the content. Once the information has been analyzed, the project coordinator proposes to the partners the measures to be taken, as well as any improvement proposals that may arise. The process is closed once the result has been communicated to the person who submitted the complaint.

4 Documented information

4.1 Document identification

Table 14 – Document identification

Type	Identification code	Interpretation	Example
Deliverables	ENTRN DEL XX.vv/YYYY	DOC/REP – initials XX – number vv – version YYYY – year	ENTRN DEL 1.1.00/2022
Documents/Reports	ENTRN DOC XX.vv/YYYY	DOC/REP – initials XX – number vv – version YYYY – year	ENTRN DOC 01.00/2022
Procedures	ENTRN PRC XX.pp/YYYY	PRC – initials XX – number pp – process number YYYY – year	ENTRN REP 01.00/2022
Records	ENTRN REC XX.vv/YYYY	REC – initials XX – number vv – version YYYY – year	ENTRN PRC 01.04/2022

4.2 Document Elaboration, Approval, Dissemination and Revision

Elaboration

All partners can elaborate a new document, procedure or record, whenever necessary, using the Project's templates (Word and PowerPoint) and the documents identification (Table 14 above).

Approval

E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators documents are approved by the Project Coordinator (PC). After producing a new document, each partner will send the proposal to the PC, so that the PC can approve it and make it available for all partners on TEAMS.

Dissemination

All the project documents will be available on EMDESK. To assure that the version in use is the latest, whenever a partner needs a new document, he/she must get the template from EMDESK. Every time that a new document is included, the Project Coordinator notifies all partners.

Revision

The documents will be revised when the partners consider that the existing ones no longer meet the initial purpose. All partners can propose changes to the documents, being its approval a responsibility of the Project Coordinator.

All deliverables will have been reviewed by a partner previous defined. The complete draft of the deliverable must be sent to the reviewer, by the responsible for the deliverable, up to 3 weeks before the deadline. Reviewers will have one week to review and sent it to the person responsible for the deliverable. The responsible for the deliverable, with the results of the review, will make the final version and sent it to the Project Coordinator up to one week before the deadline.

The list of the reviewers is presented in the following Table 15:

Table 15 – Deliverables reviewers

Deliverable (number)	Deliverable name	WP number	Lead participant	Type	Dissemination level	Deliverable date (months)	Reviewer
D1.1	Report on E ³ UDRES ² Ent-r-e-novators kick-off meeting in Setúbal	1	IPS	R	SEN	M2	MATE
D1.2	Project Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan	1	IPS	R	PU	M6	STPUAS
D1.3	Data Management Plan	1	IPS	R	SEN	M6	UPT
D1.4	Quality assurance and risk management plan	1	IPS	R	PU	M6	VIA
D1.5	Project Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication report - part 1	1	IPS	R	PU	M15	STPUAS
D1.6	Updated Data Management Plan	1	IPS	R	SEN	M19	VIA
D1.7	Report on E ³ UDRES ² Ent-r-e-novators science-policy conference	1	IPS	R	SEN	M30	UCLL
D1.8	Project Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan – part 2	1	IPS	R	PU	M36	STPUAS
D2.1	Report on E ³ UDRES ² alliance R&I landscape after two years of collaboration	2	STPUAS	R	PU	M12	IPS
D2.2	1st R&I survey report: internal scientific community	2	STPUAS	R	SEN	M12	VIA
D2.3	2nd R&I survey report: students, stakeholders and citizens	2	STPUAS	R	SEN	M18	UCLL
D2.4	E ³ UDRES ² common R&I agenda and action plan	2	STPUAS	R	PU	M36	VIA
D3.1	Open report on the current and future situation (strengths and weaknesses) of demand and supply of RD&I infrastructure and resources within the E ³ UDRES ² alliance	3	MATE	R	PU	M12	IPS

Deliverable (number)	Deliverable name	WP number	Lead participant	Type	Dissemination level	Deliverable date (months)	Reviewer
D3.2	Interactive maps of external (indirect) RD&I resources of E ³ UDRES ² institutes	3	MATE	R	SEN	M18	UPT
D3.3	Evaluation of transactional costs of using external (indirect) resources	3	MATE	R	SEN	M18	STPUAS
D3.4	Sharing network interface & synergy keypoints plan	3	MATE	R	PU	M21	UCLL
D3.5	Open report on 3-level (institutional, national and international) scenario&risk analysis	3	MATE	R	PU	M24	Via
D3.6	Strategy & implementation plan for efficient, sustainable and agile RD&I sharing network	3	MATE	R	PU	M36	UPT
D4.1	Report on the identified practices, barriers and needs for strengthening open research, open science and technology transfer between partners	4	UPT	R	PU	M8	MATE
D4.2	Development of a training curricula for providing OS/OI/OE skills and competences	4	UPT	R	PU	M12	UCLL
D4.3	OS/OI/OE strategy and implementation plan for the consortium	4	UPT	R	PU	M30	STPUAS
D4.4	Report on OS/OI/OE pilot training activities and suggestions for improvement	4	UPT	R	SEN	M36	IPS
D5.1	Models of Engagement guide	5	UCLL	R	PU	M12	UPT
D5.2	Maturity model with engagement competences and engagement incompetences	5	UCLL	R	PU	M14	MATE
D5.3	Inspiration guide with clear definitions for citizen purpose, liminal location, engagement angels and engagement rewards	5	UCLL	R	PU	M22	MATE
D5.4	Early engagement for primary and secondary schools	5	UCLL	R	SEN	M22	IPS
D5.5	I Living lab for engagement ambassadors	5	UCLL	R	SEN	M36	MATE
D6.1	Status report on E ³ UDRES ² partners' human resources for research	6	Via	R	SEN	M15	IPS
D6.2	Status report on E ³ UDRES ² R&I ecosystems	6	Via	R	SEN	M20	UPT
D6.3	E ³ UDRES ² joint human resources strategy for researchers (HRS4R)	6	Via	R	SEN	M30	IPS
D6.4	Report on connecting E ³ UDRES ² ecosystems: strategy and implementation plan	6	Via	R	PU	M36	UCLL

5 Risk management

In project management, a risk is an uncertain event or condition that, if it occurs, has a negative impact on one or more project objectives such as schedule, budget, quality, or scope. Project risks must be identified, assessed, and managed in order to minimize the negative impact and increase the likelihood of project success. Thus, risk management processes intend to avoid or to minimize the impact of external and/or internal factors that can compromise the project's development.

E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators identified 7 risks, its occurrence likelihood (risk level), the impact that each one would have on the project's implementation (impact risk), as well as the respective risk-mitigation measures. The risks are monitored every three months, as well as the mitigation measures that must be properly implemented and assessed to verify about its effectiveness. Table 16 presents the risks and respective mitigation measures as presented in the DoA.

Table 16 – Risk description and mitigation measures

Description of risk [indicate level of (i) likelihood, and (ii) severity: Low/Medium/High]	Work package(s) involved	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
R1 – Insufficient involvement of stakeholders inside of the R&I-platform (i) Medium; (ii) Medium	WP1	Focusing on target-oriented-communication, involvement of stakeholders at an early stage Define a person in charge at each institution of the consortium to make direct contacts and meetings with the Stakeholders in their region
R2 – Regional lack of support based on rigidity, strong tradition or politics slowing further development of R&I ecosystems (i) Low; (ii) Medium	WP2-WP6	Regular communication and interaction with policy makers on national and European level Ensuring the early engagement and promoting an ownership culture that motivates regional players to keep active in the construction of knowledge-based, smart and sustainable regions in cooperation with E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators
R3 – Insufficient engagement of local habitants with researchers (i) Medium; (ii) Medium	WP5	Focusing on target-oriented-communication, involvement of stakeholders at an early stage
R4 – Internal Consortium difficulties in realization (i) Low; (ii) Medium	WP1	Regular communication between partners to inform changes in partner institutions at an early stage to find a suitable solution Several physical meetings will be planned conveniently for all the partners while email and online meetings will be organized in a regular basis, to quickly resolve any anticipated or emerging difficulties
R5 – Legal/administrative barriers (i) Medium; (ii) Medium	WP1	Regular communication and interaction with policy makers on national and European level
R6 – Institutional difficulties (i) Low; (ii) Medium	WP1	Regular communication between partners to inform changes in partner institutions at an early stage to find a suitable solution.
R7 – Delays or change of plans due to COVID-19 and other external elements (i) Medium; (ii) Medium	WP1-WP6	Consider back-up plan, e.g. for events, etc.

5.1 Risk management protocol

This chapter outlines the steps for an effective risk management protocol to minimize the potential threats that may impact the success of the project objectives. The protocol consists of the following key steps:

The following steps are involved in managing project risks:

- Identification, analysis, and evaluation of potential risks
- Logging risks in the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators risk log (Annex I)
- Assigning risk owners and developing mitigation plans
- Prioritizing risks based on a scoring system
- Monitoring the progress of mitigation plans
- Escalating communication if mitigation action deadlines are not being met
- Closing out risks that have been effectively mitigated
- Continuously reviewing and updating the risk management protocol to reflect changes in the project environment, risk assessments, and response plans

With this protocol in place, risks can be identified, evaluated, and mitigated in a timely manner, ensuring the success of the project. By recording an audit trail of discussions and mitigation of project risks, the project team will be better prepared to react to changes and unforeseen events, and to make informed decisions regarding the management of risks. The audit trail will provide a comprehensive history of the risk management process, including the identification of risks, their assessment, response planning, implementation, and outcome. This information can be used to continuously improve the risk management process, enhance decision making, and increase the likelihood of project success.

Furthermore, our risk management protocol will ensure that the key stakeholders (e.g. members of the top level management who may also be represented in the general assembly) are informed and, when necessary, participate in the mitigation. Regular communication and collaboration between all stakeholders, including risk owners, project managers, and other team members, is our main strategy to ensure that risk management is integrated into the overall project process.

If a risk event materializes, it is important to respond promptly in order to minimize its impact. The following actions should be taken in coordination with the Project Coordinator, and with the involvement of the Executive Board and General Assembly as necessary:

1. Assess the situation: gather information about the risk event and determine its scope, impact, and likelihood of further occurrence.
2. Make a decision: based on the assessment, make a decision on how to respond to the risk event, taking into account the impact on the project objectives, timeline, and budget.

3. Allocate resources: if necessary, allocate resources such as additional staff, funding, or equipment to address the risk event.
4. Implement the response: this should be done as quickly and effectively as possible, using the resources that have been allocated.
5. Monitor and adjust: continuously monitor the situation and make adjustments to the response plan as necessary.
6. Communicate with stakeholders: regularly communicate with all stakeholders about the status of the risk event and the actions being taken to mitigate it.

Step 1: Risk Identification, analysis and evaluation

The leaders of each WP should present in every three months to the Project Coordinator (PC), during the WP1 meetings, the possible risks previously identified and present suggested mitigation measures. The coordinator of the project presents these possible risks during the Executive Board (EB) meetings, in every three months. The Executive Board, hearing the Project Coordinator and the WPs leaders, will evaluate the pertinence of the risks and the adequacy of the measurement measures and will decide whether they will be considered and whether the measures are adequate or need to be revised. For risks assessed as relevant, they will be added to the already identified project risks and the respective mitigation measures approved by the Project Coordinator and the EB will be considered in project management. If there is any difficulty in deciding about the risks presented, the problem will be put to the General Assembly (GnA), which will make the final decision. These new risks and related procedures will be included in the updated MONITORING AND EVALUATION PLAN.

WP leaders are responsible for continuously monitoring the progress along the objectives in their work packages.

Risks are continuously monitored by the project coordinator and leader of WP1, consulting each WP leader.

The leaders of each WP should present in every three months to the Project Coordinator (PC), during the WP1 meetings, the status of each identified risk. The project coordinator presents an overview of the status of each risk during each Executive Board meeting.

If there is any risk that is likely to occur, the Executive Board will discuss how to implement the planned or will define new mitigation measures. If it is not possible to solve the problem within the EB, then the problem will be presented to the GnA who will decide what to do.

Step 2: Logging risks in the risk log

The WP1 team developed a risk log for the project, drawing inspiration from resources available online from the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention.² The E³UDRES² Ent-re-novators risk log was created in Microsoft Excel and will serve as the central repository for managing and tracking risks. The log will be updated and uploaded to EMDESK after each quarterly review in WP1 meetings.

As shown in table 17 (instructions taken from our risk management excel file), the risk log records information related to identified risks, the main one being:

- Description of the risk
- Impact and likelihood of the risk
- Current status of the risk
- Risk owner
- Response plan and mitigation measures

Table 17 – Instructions taken from E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators risk management log

RISK MANAGEMENT LOG	
Column	Instructions For Completing This Document
For each risk identified, complete the following:	
A	ID: A unique ID number used to identify the risk in the risk tracking log
B	WP: The work package(s) that identified the risk
C	Current Status: This column should be populated with the risk's current status <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Open: The risk is currently open but is not yet an issue o Closed: The risk is no longer considered an active project threat and can be closed with or without resolution
D	Risk Impact: This column should be populated with the potential impact of the risk if it did become a project issue Valid options include the following: Insignificant (1), Minor (2), Moderate (3), Major (4), Catastrophic (5)
E	Risk probability: This column should be populated with the estimated probability that the risk will at some point become a project issue (probability of occurrence) Valid options include: Rare (1), Unlikely (2), Possible (3), Likely (4) and Almost certain (5)
F	Risk priority: Assignment of color codes according to the risk matrix below (to the right)
G	Risk Description: This column should be populated with a description of the risk
H	Risk Owner: This column should be populated with the name of the person(s) who will be responsible to manage the risk
I	Project Impact: This column should be populated with a description of the potential project impact as a result of the risk
J	Risk Area: This column should be populated with the appropriate risk area

² <https://www2.cdc.gov/cdcup/library/matrix/default.htm> (latest accessed on February 6th, 2023)

RISK MANAGEMENT LOG

Column	Instructions For Completing This Document
K	Symptoms: This column should be populated with the symptoms of risk that may eventually lead to the execution of a risk contingency plan
L	Triggers: This column should be populated with the triggers that would indicate the requirement to execute contingency plans
M	Risk Response Strategy: This column should be populated with the preferred risk response strategy
N	Response Strategy: This column should be populated an appropriate response strategy to prevent the risk from becoming an issue
O	Contingency Plan: This column should be populated with a description of the risk contingency plan

Step 3: Risk owners and mitigation (response) plans

Risk owners will be tasked with managing designated risks. The Project Coordinator can assign a risk to a work package leader, to a WP team member or to the full team working on a specific WP. In cases where the risk can be managed at an operational level, the risk owners will typically be those involved in the work package that either discovered the risk or is most likely to be impacted by it. General project management risks should be handled by the project coordinator and his team. However, the project coordinator may attribute the ownership to a local WP1 representative or team (WP1 teams of the partner institutions), when the risk is confined to that institution and/or can be better managed internally. Risk owners will be assigned during quarterly reviews and discussion of the risk management plan in WP1 meetings, unless the urgency of the risk determines otherwise. In that case, WP leaders should contact the Project Coordinator as soon as suspect of a more serious risk appears.

The risk owners will play a crucial role in the risk management process as they will be accountable for ensuring that appropriate mitigation plans are developed and implemented.

During or immediately after discussion in a quarterly WP1 meeting, the risk owner should complete the register of the risk (in the risk log) indicating: the potential impact of the risk on the project, the risk area (drop-down menu), the symptoms and triggers, the risk response strategy (acceptance, avoidance, contingency, mitigation or transfer) and either the response strategy or the contingency plan.

- Mitigation actions should describe the specific actions that will be taken to prevent reduce the impact of a risk if it occurs.
- Contingency plans define responses to identified triggers, when they materialise, in the expectation of reducing the impact of the corresponding risk on the project.

- Transfer is a response that shifts responsibility to another party (e.g. a risk may be transferred to an institution, outside the scope of the project – e.g. unforeseen extra costs)
- Avoidance means changing the course of the project to eliminate the threat from an identified risk. However, this can only be applied in very limited situations because, under the Grant Agreement, we are obliged to follow exactly what has been planned in the Description of Action (DoA).
- Acceptance involves acknowledging the risk as part of the project and accepting its consequences. This might be the case of external risks (legal, regulatory, etc) that are out of control for the project team and/or for the partner institutions.

These plans will be developed by the risk owner in collaboration with its team and may include a combination of risk mitigation strategies, such as transferring the risk to another party, accepting the risk, or avoiding the risk altogether. The risk owner will be responsible for monitoring the status of the mitigation plan, regularly reviewing it to ensure that it remains relevant and effective, and reporting back to the project coordinator on the progress of risk mitigation efforts, on a quarterly basis and on WP1 meeting. Whenever necessary, risks will be discussed also in Executive Board and/or General Assembly meetings. By assigning risk owners and developing mitigation plans, we will ensure that all risks are managed in an organized and effective manner, which will reduce the impact of risk events and increase the chances of project success.

Step 4: Prioritization of risks

We will prioritize risks using a control (or risk assessment) matrix (Table 18), which is a grid that assesses the probability of a risk to materialise against the potential impact of that same risks, in terms of time, cost, quality, and other relevant project objectives. The matrix assigns a color code to each risk, with red indicating the highest priority risks that require immediate attention, yellow and pink representing moderate risk that need to be closely monitored, and green indicating low risk that may not require immediate attention but still need to be monitored. This colour-code will help our team to quickly and effectively prioritize the risks and allocate resources to mitigate the most critical ones.

Table 18 – Risk matrix used to prioritize the project risks (taken from the risk management log instructions)

IMPACT	Catastrophic	5	5	10	15	20	25
	Major	4	4	8	12	16	20
	Moderate	3	3	6	9	12	15
	Minor	2	2	4	6	8	10
	Insignificant	1	1	2	3	4	5
			1	2	3	4	5
			Rare	Unlikely	Possible	Likely	Almost certain
PROBABILITY							

Figure 8 – Flowchart of Risk Identification, assessment, mitigation, monitoring and control

5.2 Risk update according to the first six months of project development

According to the protocol mentioned above, new risks were identified, and the respective mitigation measures proposed. So, Table 16 was updated giving rise to Table 19.

Table 19 – Risk description and mitigation measures (update)

Description of risk [indicate level of (i) likelihood, and (ii) severity: Low/Medium/High]	Work package(s) involved	Proposed risk-mitigation measures	Risk area(s)
R1 – Insufficient involvement of stakeholders inside of the R&I-platform (i) Medium; (ii) Medium	WP1	Focusing on target-oriented-communication, involvement of stakeholders at an early stage Define a person in charge at each institution of the consortium to make direct contacts and meetings with the Stakeholders in their region	Communication and data / information
R2 – Regional lack of support based on rigidity, strong tradition or politics slowing further development of R&I ecosystems (i) Low; (ii) Medium	WP2-WP6	Regular communication and interaction with policy makers on national and European level Ensuring the early engagement and promoting an ownership culture that motivates regional players to keep active in the construction of knowledge-based, smart and sustainable regions in cooperation with E3UDRES2 Ent r e novators	Communication and data / information
R3 – Insufficient engagement of local habitants with researchers (i) Medium; (ii) Medium	WP5	Focusing on target-oriented-communication, involvement of stakeholders at an early stage	Communication and data / information
R4 – Internal Consortium difficulties in realization (i) Low; (ii) Medium	WP1	Regular communication between partners to inform changes in partner institutions at an early stage to find a suitable solution Several physical meetings will be planned conveniently for all the partners while email and online meetings will be organized in a regular basis, to quickly resolve any anticipated or emerging difficulties	Organizational / Communication
R5 – Legal/administrative barriers (i) Medium; (ii) Medium	WP1	Regular communication and interaction with policy makers on national and European level	Institutional support / Communication
R6 – Institutional difficulties (i) Low; (ii) Medium	WP1	Regular communication between partners to inform changes in partner institutions at an early stage to find a suitable solution Top management (rectors, vice-rectors) involvement in GnA to ensure institutional support for the project team	Institutional support / Communication

Description of risk [indicate level of (i) likelihood, and (ii) severity: Low/Medium/High]	Work package(s) involved	Proposed risk-mitigation measures	Risk área(s)
R7 – Delays or change of plans due to COVID-19 and other external elements (i) Medium; (ii) Medium	WP1-WP6	Consider back-up plan, e.g. for events, etc.	Project management
R8 – A partner is unable to deliver results or gather information on time, including late deliverables or missed milestones (i) Low; (ii) Medium	WP2-WP6	Regular WP1 and Executive Board meetings are being held to ensure that the tasks in each WP are clearly defined and responsibilities assigned and distributed over the representatives of the 6 partner institutions on each WP	Team performance
R9 – Inefficient or ineffective team member (or leaving key persons) (i) Low; (ii) Medium	WP1-WP6	If the WP leader detect this issue, will inform the PC, and the PC will ask to the institution leader to reinforce the team in cause	Team performance
R10 – Unforeseen lack of resources (i) Low; (ii) High	WP1-WP6	To handle with the financial resources issue, the partners in the GnA will vote and decide about the possibility of redistributing budget or whether other measures could be undertaken.	Budget / Project resources
R11 – A partner leaves the project (i) Low; (ii) High	WP1-WP6	In case of partner withdrawal, the other partners will reinforce all WPs teams, and in the GnA will vote who will replace in the leadership of the respective WP to assure the achievement the planned objectives of the project	Organizational / Change management
R12 – Low participation in ENTRN workshops (i) Medium; (ii) Low	WP4; WP5	The workshops will be recorded to be shared in the project website to achieve higher audiences If the number of registrations some days before is low, the event promotion will be reinforced The promotion reinforce will also be applied in the future workshops	Communication and data / information

ANNEX I | Project Risk Management Log

ent.r.e. novators					Project No. 101071317					Funded by the European Union				
RISK MANAGEMENT LOG														
ID	Work Package	Current Status	Risk Impact	Probability of occurrence	Risk priority	Risk Description	Risk owner	Project Impact	Risk Area	Symptoms	Triggers	Risk Response Strategy	Response Strategy	Contingency Plan
R1	WP1	Open	Insignificant	Unlikely	2									
R2			Minor	Possible	6									
R3			Major	Possible	12									
R4			Catastrophic	Almost certain	25									
R5														
R6														
R7														
R8														
R9														
R10														

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novators**
ENTREPRENEURS + RESEARCHERS
EDUCATORS + INNOVATORS

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